

Smarandache Lucky Math

by C. Ashbacher
C. Ashbacher Technologies
Hiawatha, Box 294
IA 52233, USA
E-mail: 71603.522@compuserve.com

The Smarandache Lucky Method/Algorithm/Operation/etc. is said to be any incorrect method or algorithm or operation etc. which leads to a correct result. The wrong calculation should be fun, somehow similarly to the students' common mistakes, or to produce confusions or paradoxes.

Can someone give an example of a Smarandache Lucky Derivation, or Integration, or Solution to a Differential Equation?

Reference:

- [1] Smarandache, Florentin, "Collected Papers" (Vol. II), University of Kishinev, 1997, p.200.